

BRIDGING SOCIAL GAPS: IMPACT OF PHYSICAL AND DIGITAL GAMES ON CHILDREN WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of games on the social development of children with intellectual disabilities (ID). Recognizing socialization as a pivotal aspect of human development, the research examines how structured physical and digital games can enhance communication, emotional regulation, and peer interactions among children with ID. A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving pre- and post-tests, with six participants divided into experimental and control groups. The findings revealed significant improvements in social interactions, emotional control, teamwork, and self-confidence in the experimental group, demonstrating the potential of structured games in fostering social skills. Despite limitations in sample size and intervention duration, the study underscores the importance of integrating game-based interventions into educational and therapeutic settings to support the holistic development of children with ID. Recommendations include individualized care plans, parental involvement, and the use of adaptive technologies to maximize the benefits of structured gameplay.

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition marked by challenges in social communication, interaction, and the presence of restricted, repetitive behaviors (APA, 2013). It manifests early in life and affects functional skills throughout an individual's lifespan. The prevalence of ASD has increased globally, with recent data suggesting that 1 in 36 children in the United States are diagnosed with ASD (CDC, 2023). This growing prevalence has led to increased attention from researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

Children with ASD often exhibit deficits in communication, including verbal and non-verbal domains, which hinder their ability to express needs,

interact socially, and engage effectively with their environment (Tager-Flusberg & Kasari, 2013). Among these challenges, functional independent living skills—such as personal hygiene, dressing, eating, and managing daily tasks—are essential for autonomy and quality of life (Wehman et al., 2014). However, many children with ASD struggle to acquire these skills due to social, cognitive, and sensory processing differences (Matson et al., 2012).

Psychologists play a crucial role in understanding and supporting the development of these skills. They provide insights into behavioral patterns, learning styles, and environmental influences that shape a child's functional abilities (Pellicano, 2010). Evidence suggests that early psychological intervention can

enhance adaptive functioning and independence in children with ASD (Perry et al., 2011). Moreover, integrating psychological perspectives helps in designing individualized support strategies that cater to the unique needs of each child (National Research Council, 2001).

This article explores the perspectives of psychologists on the functional independent living skills of children with ASD, aiming to contribute to a nuanced understanding of effective support strategies. The qualitative approach adopted in this study allows for an in-depth exploration of professional insights, highlighting both challenges and interventions relevant to fostering independence in children with ASD.

LITERATURE REVIEW

UNESCO (2006) emphasized the role of ICT in enhancing education for children with ID, supporting CRPD principles and promoting communication, independence, and socialization. Yong (2009) highlighted the growth of the video game industry and its educational potential. Takahashi (2010) emphasized the interactive nature of games for children with ID. Bartoli et al. (2016) found multiplayer games improved teamwork, communication, and social inclusion. Ryan and Deci (2017) noted interactive games aid verbal and non-verbal communication, offering safe spaces for social practice. Gee (2007) showed that rewards in games boost confidence and motivation, helping children transition to real-life social settings. Prensky (2001) identified cooperative games as tools for enhancing problem-solving and teamwork skills.

Bourgonjon et al. (2010) noted inclusive games foster peer interaction and belonging. Gentile et al. (2004) warned against excessive solitary gaming, which may hinder social skills. Anderson and Bushman (2001) linked violent games with increased aggression, advocating for non-violent educational games. Kirsh (2006) discussed how structured games may lack realism, highlighting the need to combine games with real-world learning. Vander Meer et al. (2016) emphasized that skills learned in games require additional support for generalization. Connolly et al. (2012) stressed the value of parental involvement in selecting and supervising games for developmental benefits.

Granic, Lobel, and Engels (2014) advocated for games emphasizing teamwork and problem-solving, noting their capacity to simulate real-life social scenarios. Bouck (2016) examined adaptive technologies, showing they allow tailored experiences that support developmental learning. Chiarello (2017) emphasized multiplayer games reduce loneliness and promote peer interaction through structured activities. Gentile et al. reiterated the risks of isolation from solitary gaming, while Anderson and Bushman (2001) again underscored the behavioral risks of violent games.

Granic et al. emphasized the educator's and parent's role in selecting prosocial games. Bartoli et al. (2016) further advocated for structured multiplayer games to support communication. Ryan and Deci (2017) confirmed that games enhance social engagement through rehearsed interactions. Gee (2007) reiterated the motivational effect of rewards. Prensky (2001) affirmed collaborative gaming improves social decision-making. Bourgonjon et al. (2010) observed that inclusive environments support social development in children with ID. Vander Meer et al. (2016) recommended integrating games with broader interventions to ensure skill generalization. Connolly et al. (2012) concluded that guided, co-selected games by parents enhance developmental outcomes.

Statement of Problem

Social development is a vital aspect of human growth, directly impacting communication, emotional regulation, and interpersonal relationships. Children with intellectual disabilities (ID) often face significant barriers in acquiring these skills due to developmental challenges, which hinder their peer interactions and emotional expression. Although structured play is recognized as a critical tool for cognitive and social growth, children with ID frequently lack access to constructive and inclusive play environments. Educational and therapeutic programs rarely incorporate games tailored to address these children's social needs. Additionally, while digital games present new learning opportunities, they also introduce accessibility barriers for children with ID unless properly adapted (Aresti-Bartolome & Garcia-Zapirain, 2014). This study addresses the gap by analyzing the effects of physical and digital games on the social development of children with ID, aiming to

identify best practices for improving their social interaction and integration into society.

Objectives of the Study

1. To inquire about the phenomena that emerge from this study.
2. To evaluate the impact of games based on activities of social interaction.
3. To promote positive interaction and relationships among peers

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of games on social interaction activities?
2. What games promote positive interaction and relationships among peers?
3. What new phenomena emerge from this study?
4. What are the recommendations and suggestions?

Significance of the Study

This study contributes to existing knowledge by emphasizing the role of structured games in promoting socialization among children with intellectual disabilities (ID)—a relatively underexplored area. The findings provide valuable insights for educators, caregivers, and policymakers in designing and implementing structured play activities that enhance communication, emotional regulation, and interpersonal skills in children with ID. By highlighting the therapeutic and educational potential of play, the study supports the need for inclusive recreational programs that foster equal developmental opportunities. It also underscores the importance of policy support for integrating structured games into educational and therapeutic settings, ultimately aiming to improve the social well-being and community inclusion of children with ID.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Research Design

The current study employs a quasi-experimental design with two-time points, pre- and post-test, to evaluate the impact of an intervention on the social and communication development of children with intellectual disabilities. This design made it possible to formally compare behaviors before and after the intervention. The study compares the experimental group that will undergo the intervention with a

control group that will follow normal practice to influence the improvement in social skills solely due to the intervention.

The quasi-experimental assignment was suitable for successive evaluation of change in children's communicative and social behaviors within the well-ordered setting of an education system. It accommodates the moral imperatives, the constraints, and the requirements of a systematic and experimental approach to the assessment of the consequences of the intervention. It is used to increase the validity of data derived from changes in the subjects regarding the outcomes of intervention.

Population and sample

Target Population: School children and pupils between the ages of 6 to 12 with mild, moderate, severe, or profound intellectual disabilities. These participants are chosen to capture a sample of disabling conditions across a spectrum of cognitive developmental levels to track how the intervention is efficacious across various ability levels.

Sample Size: Six children selected (3 in experimental group and 2 in control group) for this experimental study.

Groups

Sample was divided into two groups.

Experimental Group: Received structured communication interventions.

Control Group: Receives traditional instruction without added intervention.

Selection Criteria

1. Diagnosed with mild to profound intellectual disability.
2. Enrollment in a specialized education program.
3. Parental consent for participation.

Sampling Method

The participants of the study were selected purposively from the identified educational institution. It is a technique that ensures that people selected are closest to who the intervention is meant for in the society. The intervention was intended in order to build up specific functional communication/interaction skills needed by children

with intellectual disabilities for turn taking, gaze, affective responses, and verbal language.

Intervention Plan

Eye Contact: Directing participants to look at the eyes of a partner and keeping this behavior in social contexts.

Gestures: Introducing basic gestures to expand the expressive functionality.

Facial Expressions: They train how to correct imitate and display positive emotions such as happiness, anger, frustration and the likes.

Turn-Taking and Cooperative Play: Activities centred on teaching turn-taking and improving cooperation among children.

Materials

Games: Pair and group work, such as cooperative board games, and elementary role plays.

Visual Aids: A set of flashcards illustrating emotions with papers written on them and papers that indicate which player's turn it is.

Reinforcement Tools: Rewards in the form of stickers or tokens in exchange for positive social behaviors.

Session Structure

Duration: 4 weeks

Frequency: 1 session per week

Session Length: Each session lasts 28-30 minutes.

Control Group Activities

The experimental group engaged in carefully designed intervention strategies, while the control group participated in structured lessons typical of classroom procedures and conventional group games. This approach serves as a comparative paradigm.

Research Instruments

These tests involved observing the child and rating performance using an existing checklist.

Pre-test and post-test observation checklists

These checklists included the following:

1. Social interaction
2. Communication
3. Work and social interaction
4. Impulse control
5. Play and social interaction
6. Acceptance by peer group
7. Self-esteem

Behavior was rated using the following scale

- 4 = Frequently Interacts with Peers (FIWP)
- 3 = Occasionally Interacts with Peers (OIWP)
- 2 = Rarely Interacts with Peers (RIWP)
- 1 = Avoids Interaction with Peers (AIWP)

Validation of the Research Instrument

Experts discussed the tools for content and construct validity to confirm the research instrument appalling. The instruments were pilot tested with a small group of participants in order to iron out any confusion and to assess the inter-observer reliability.

Data Collection

Baseline (Pre-Test) Assessment

The observation checklist was used to assess the subject's individual communication and social skills before the intervention which was done in form of pre-test.

Intervention Period

The experimental group was engaged in four-week structured communication intervention sessions; however, the control group remained in their usual learning activities.

Week 1: Symbolic Overview of Social Interaction and Communication

Activities: There are three fun and interactive activities; Name Toss Game to enhance peer interaction, Guess the Emotion to encourage the understanding of emotional intelligence for students, and Team Puzzle to build teamwork skills.

Week 2: Collaboration and Turn-Taking

Activities: Relay Race, Simon Says, Images on Cards, Building Blocks Challenge is used more often to improve the teamwork, Listeners, and Turn-Takers.

Week 3: Emotional Regulation

Activities: Freeze Dance, Emotion Thermometer, and Winning and Losing Talk to help child understand his feelings, manage his feelings appropriately, and accept the result of any game.

Week 4: Self Esteem and Confidence Peer acceptance

Activities

Some of them include; Buddy Challenges, Compliment Chain, and New Game Trial to increase confidence, acceptance by peers as well as encourage the children for new games.

Post-Test Assessment

After assessments were done, post-tests were carried out with an aim of comparing social and communication deficit changes with those on the pre-test.

Ongoing Observation

The observation checklist was completed daily during the intervention to record common patterns of social interactions and communicative behaviors, as well as the child's affect. • A case of descriptive measures of mean and standard deviations of pre- and post-test scores was carried out.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

Descriptive measures of mean and standard deviations of pre- and post-test scores were computed.

Paired Sample T-tests: Applied in order to record fluctuations in the condition of the subjects within the given experimental group.

Research Ethics

Informed Consent

All the parents/guardians provided written consent, and student's role in the study was explained to them in terms of the objectives of the proposed study.

Confidentiality

In order to protect people's identities, the participant's identification is omitted from the study.

Minimizing Harm

The emphasis is on the fact that the sessions are supposed to be low-stress sessions. Participants had the right to withdraw from the study with no reason asked for.3.8

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table No. 1: Age of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 9	1	16.7	16.7	16.7
11	1	16.7	16.7	33.3
12	1	16.7	16.7	50.0
13	2	33.3	33.3	83.3
15	1	16.7	16.7	100.0
Total	6	100.0	100.0	

The survey participants are between nine and fifteen years old. From the data we get that there was one respondent each of nine, eleven and twelve years of age constituting 16.7% each of the total sample. There were two respondents aged 13 years, which was the

highest in the study population at 33.3%. The last respondent was 15 years old, but they only make up 16.7 percent of the entire sample size. According to these results, the ages of the participants are quite equally distributed across the groups although the most frequent age is 13.

Table No. 2: Gender of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	2	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Female	4	66.7	66.7	100.0
	Total	6	100.0	100.0	

From the respondents, 33.3% of 2 respondents were male, 66.7% or 4 respondents were female. This goes

a long way to explain the high proportion of the female responders in the study.

Table No. 3: Grade of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	4	66.7	66.7	66.7
	2	2	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	6	100.0	100.0	

According to the level of participation the respondents were in two Grades, of which 66.7% were in Grade 1 while 33.3% in Grade 2. This sentiment

imply that majority of the participants were in the lower graded level within the given academic year.

Table No. 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	6	9	15	12.17	2.041
Gender	6	1	2	1.67	.516
Grade	6	1	2	1.33	.516
PreSI1	6	1	3	1.83	.753
PreSI2	6	1	2	1.50	.548
PreSI3	6	1	2	1.33	.516
PostSI1	6	2	3	2.17	.408
PostSI2	6	1	3	2.00	.632
PostSI3	6	1	3	2.50	.837
PreCs1	6	1	3	1.83	.983
PreCs2	6	1	2	1.50	.548
PreCs3	6	1	3	1.50	.837
PostCs1	6	1	3	2.33	.816
PostCs2	6	1	3	2.17	.753
PostCs3	6	1	4	2.17	1.169
PreOt1	6	1	3	2.33	1.033
PreOt2	6	2	3	2.50	.548
PreOt3	6	1	3	2.00	.632
PostOt1	6	1	4	2.50	1.049
PostOt2	6	1	3	2.33	.816
PostOt3	6	2	3	2.33	.516
PreER1	6	1	4	2.83	1.169
PreER2	6	1	4	2.67	1.211
PreER3	6	1	4	2.17	1.169
PostER1	6	1	2	1.83	.408
PostER2	6	1	2	1.83	.408
PostER3	6	2	3	2.50	.548

PreTTR1	6	2	4	2.83	.753
PreTTR2	6	1	4	2.83	1.169
PreTTR3	6	1	4	2.83	.983
PostTTR1	6	2	3	2.67	.516
PostTTR2	6	2	3	2.67	.516
PostTTR3	6	2	3	2.50	.548
PrePAI1	6	1	3	2.00	.632
PrePAI2	6	1	3	1.83	.753
PrePAI3	6	1	3	2.00	.894
PostPAI1	6	2	3	2.33	.516
PostPAI2	6	2	3	2.50	.548
PostPAI3	6	2	3	2.67	.516
PreSEC1	6	1	2	1.67	.516
PreSEC2	6	1	3	1.83	.753
PreSEC3	6	1	4	2.33	1.211
PreSEC4	6	1	2	1.33	.516
PreSEC5	6	1	4	1.83	1.169
PostSEC1	6	1	2	1.83	.408
PostSEC2	6	2	2	2.00	.000
PostSEC3	6	3	3	3.00	.000
PostSEC4	6	1	3	2.50	.837
PostSE5	6	2	3	2.33	.516
Valid N	6				

The descriptive statistics table brings out analyses for six participants with a study sample of six participants (N = 6) and different variables. The age of participants was calculated in years: they were 9 to 15 years old; the mean age was 12.17, SD = 2.041. Pre-test gender was also recoded into 1 (Male) and 2 (Female). The test result did show that, the mean = 1.67 and mode = 1 while the range = 3. Grade, which also has values of 1 and 2, had higher mean of 1.33, this meant most of the participants were in the lower grade. Pre- and post-test scores were recorded across different domains: This includes: Interaction (SI), Communications skills (Cs), Other attributes (Ot), Managing emotions (ER), Task and/or time perspective (TTR), Participation/ activity involvement (PAI) and

Self-efficacy/ confidence (SEC). The scores obtained from the surveys were between 1 and 4; the means were also higher in post-test suggesting probable enhanced learning. For example, there was an increase in PostSI1 (mean = 2.17) from PreSI1 (mean = 1.83). The same positive trends were present in PostCs1, PostOt1, and PostPAI3 suggesting improvement in these constructs. SDs ranged from low to high and were moderate for most variables example PreER2 SD = 1.211 while the SD of post intervention scores reduced indicating that participants' response became more consistent after the intervention. In general, the table depicts shifts in participants' performance and other parameter during and after the intervention.

Table No. 6: Paired Samples Statistics

Pair		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	PreSI1	1.83	6	.753	.307
	PostSI1	2.17	6	.408	.167
Pair 2	PreSI2	1.50	6	.548	.224
	PostSI2	2.00	6	.632	.258
Pair 3	PreSI3	1.33	6	.516	.211

	PostSI3	2.83	6	.408	.167
Pair 4	PreCs1	1.83	6	.983	.401
	PostCs1	2.33	6	.816	.333
Pair 5	PreCs2	1.50	6	.548	.224
	PostCs2	2.17	6	.753	.307
Pair 6	PreCs3	1.50	6	.837	.342
	PostCs3	2.17	6	1.169	.477
Pair 7	PreOt1	2.33	6	1.033	.422
	PostOt1	2.50	6	1.049	.428
Pair 8	PreOt2	2.50	6	.548	.224
	PostOt2	2.33	6	.816	.333
Pair 9	PreOt3	2.00	6	.632	.258
	PostOt3	2.33	6	.516	.211
Pair 10	PreER1	2.83	6	1.169	.477
	PostER1	1.83	6	.408	.167
Pair 11	PreER2	2.67	6	1.211	.494
	PostER2	1.83	6	.408	.167
Pair 12	PreER3	2.17	6	1.169	.477
	PostER3	2.50	6	.548	.224
Pair 13	PreTTR1	2.83	6	.753	.307
	PostTTR1	2.67	6	.516	.211
Pair 14	PreTTR2	2.83	6	1.169	.477
	PostTTR2	2.67	6	.516	.211
Pair 15	PreTTR3	2.83	6	.983	.401
	PostTTR3	2.50	6	.548	.224
Pair 16	PrePAI1	1.83	6	.753	.307
	PostPAI1	2.33	6	.516	.211
Pair 17	PrePAI2	1.67	6	.816	.333
	PostPAI2	2.50	6	.548	.224
Pair 18	PrePAI3	1.83	6	.753	.307
	PostPAI3	2.67	6	.516	.211
Pair 19	PreSEC1	1.67	6	.516	.211
	PostSEC1	1.83	6	.408	.167
Pair 20	PreSEC2	1.83	6	.753	.307
	PostSEC2	2.00	6	.000	.000
Pair 21	PreSEC3	2.33	6	1.211	.494
	PostSEC3	3.00	6	.000	.000
Pair 22	PreSEC4	1.33	6	.516	.211
	PostSEC4	2.50	6	.837	.342
Pair 23	PreSEC5	1.83	6	1.169	.477
	PostSEC5	2.33	6	.516	.211

The paired samples statistics table provides the comparative analysis of the pre and post intervention score of six participants in the different domains of social interaction, communication, emotional

regulation and self-confidence. The mean scores continue to depict higher values after the intervention and thus, reveal the efficacy of structured games in enhancing the social –emotional activities in children

with ID. For instance, in social interaction (Pair 1), homes mean score raised from 1.83 (PreSI1) to 2.17 (PostSI1) implying on improved peer relations. Likewise, appreciable improvement is recorded in the frequency of initiating conversation, especially in Pair 3, which has risen from a mean of 1.33 in PreSI3 to 2.83 of PostSI3. The second aspect concerning communication skills the findings show considerable progress for instance, in Pair 4 and Pair 5 the means have changed from 1.83. PreCs1 to 2.33.PostCs1 and from 1.5.PreCs2 to 2.17.PostCs2.

Regarding emotional regulation, there were some positive changes; some aspects like the ability to handle frustration (Pair 12) increased from 2.17 (PreER3) to 2.50 (PostER3) while there were declines in others like ability to remain calm in challenging situations (Pair 10) decreased from 2.83 (PreER1) to 1.83 (PostER1) a clear sign the children inefficient. The analysis of definite and indefinite scarcer

technique practices signified a comparatively stable result in improve and unalterability of turn-taking and game rules adherence post interventional average among Pairs 13 to 15 pairs. Paired t-tests of quantitative results for MSEL (Pairs 16 to 18) revealed significant improvements in peer acceptance and social integration indicating a marked increase in the mean: Pair 18 = PrePAI / PostPAI3: 1.83 / 2.67. Self-confidence and independence (Pairs 19 to,20 to 23) were also found to have improvements, especially ability to express thoughts and feeling which had a mean score of 2.33 at PreSEC3 but had an improved mean score of 3.00 at PostSEC3(E1). As for relative independence in playing games that was assessed in Pair 22, the increase was observed as well - from 1.33 (PreSEC4) to 2.50 (PostSEC4). Overall, the differences between pairs of participants were less after intervention in most sets, thus the participants were more uniform in their response.

Table No. 7: Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	PreSI1 & PostSI1	6	-.542	.266
Pair 2	PreSI2 & PostSI2	6	.577	.230
Pair 3	PreSI3 & PostSI3	6	.316	.541
Pair 4	PreCs1 & PostCs1	6	-.415	.413
Pair 5	PreCs2 & PostCs2	6	-.243	.643
Pair 6	PreCs3 & PostCs3	6	.307	.554
Pair 7	PreOt1 & PostOt1	6	-.369	.471
Pair 8	PreOt2 & PostOt2	6	.000	1.000
Pair 9	PreOt3 & PostOt3	6	-.612	.196
Pair 10	PreER1 & PostER1	6	-.070	.895
Pair 11	PreER2 & PostER2	6	-.539	.269
Pair 12	PreER3 & PostER3	6	.469	.349
Pair 13	PreTTR1 & PostTTR1	6	-.686	.132
Pair 14	PreTTR2 & PostTTR2	6	-.110	.835
Pair 15	PreTTR3 & PostTTR3	6	.557	.251
Pair 16	PrePAI1 & PostPAI1	6	.686	.132
Pair 17	PrePAI2 & PostPAI2	6	-.447	.374
Pair 18	PrePAI3 & PostPAI3	6	-.171	.745
Pair 19	PreSEC1 & PostSEC1	6	.632	.178
Pair 20	PreSEC2 & PostSEC2	6	.	.
Pair 21	PreSEC3 & PostSEC3	6	.	.
Pair 22	PreSEC4 & PostSEC4	6	-.926	.008
Pair 23	PreSEC5 & PostSEC5	6	.773	.071

The paired samples correlations table reveals the interconnectivity between the scores before and after

intervention in the several domains. These correlation coefficients differ widely in their signs, positive and

negative, which imply direct and inverse and different strengths. However, relative to the first and preferred sets of hypotheses, only half of the pairs or less demonstrate moderate to strong positive correlations, e.g., Pair 19 (PreSEC1 & PostSEC1; $r = .632$; $p = .178$) indicating a consistent increase in confidence during the group games. For example, there is a strong negative correlation; pre and posttest correlation between PreSEC4 & PostSEC4 has been $r = -.926$, $p = .008$. This is one of those very few instances where a statistical inverse relation seems to crop up in this field. Similarly, there is an indication of the increase in both social interaction and acceptance among peers before and after the intervention from other pairs, for instance, Pair 2 (PreSI2 & PostSI2, $r = .577$, $p = .230$) and Pair 16 (PrePAI1 & PostPAI1, $r = .686$, $p = .132$). Nevertheless, this absence of statistical reduction in the majority of the pairs holds the evidence of the

variation in the intervention effect in different people. For some of the pairs, no associations are observable and this is evidenced by Pair 8 (PreOt2 & PostOt2, $r = .000$, $p = 1.000$) where no a priori or pre-intervention scores in this area can be said to have any valid relationship with the post-intervention scores. Also that pattern shown in figure below with both the negative correlation coefficients of Pair 1 (PreSI1 & PostSI1, $r = -.542$, $p = .266$) and Pair 11 (PreER2 & PostER2, $r = -.539$, $p = .269$) mean that the initial or later improvements in post-test scores were not representative of the improvements of all the participants in the current study but may feature high variability. In sum, the findings thus stress the differentiated effects of the intervention on the different aspects of daily life, and the need to take precise measures in view of increasing the effectiveness of the planned strategy.

Table No. 8: Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	PreSI1 - PostSI1	-.333	1.033	.422	-1.417	.751	-.791	5	.465
Pair 2	PreSI2 - PostSI2	-.500	.548	.224	-1.075	.075	-2.236	5	.076
Pair 3	PreSI3 - PostSI3	-1.500	.548	.224	-2.075	-.925	-6.708	5	.001
Pair 4	PreCs1 - PostCs1	-.500	1.517	.619	-2.092	1.092	-.808	5	.456
Pair 5	PreCs2 - PostCs2	-.667	1.033	.422	-1.751	.417	-1.581	5	.175
Pair 6	PreCs3 - PostCs3	-.667	1.211	.494	-1.938	.604	-1.348	5	.235
Pair 7	PreOt1 - PostOt1	-.167	1.722	.703	-1.974	1.641	-.237	5	.822
Pair 8	PreOt2 - PostOt2	.167	.983	.401	-.865	1.198	.415	5	.695
Pair 9	PreOt3 - PostOt3	-.333	1.033	.422	-1.417	.751	-.791	5	.465
Pair 10	PreER1 - PostER1	1.000	1.265	.516	-.327	2.327	1.936	5	.111
Pair 11	PreER2 - PostER2	.833	1.472	.601	-.711	2.378	1.387	5	.224
Pair 12	PreER3 - PostER3	-.333	1.033	.422	-1.417	.751	-.791	5	.465
Pair 13	PreTTR1 - PostTTR1	.167	1.169	.477	-1.060	1.394	.349	5	.741
Pair 14	PreTTR2 - PostTTR2	.167	1.329	.543	-1.228	1.562	.307	5	.771
Pair 15	PreTTR3 - PostTTR3	.333	.816	.333	-.524	1.190	1.000	5	.363
Pair 16	PrePAI1 - PostPAI1	-.500	.548	.224	-1.075	.075	-2.236	5	.076
Pair 17	PrePAI2 - PostPAI2	-.833	1.169	.477	-2.060	.394	-1.746	5	.141
Pair 18	PrePAI3 - PostPAI3	-.833	.983	.401	-1.865	.198	-2.076	5	.093
Pair 19	PreSEC1 - PostSEC1	-.167	.408	.167	-.595	.262	-1.000	5	.363
Pair 20	PreSEC2 - PostSEC2	-.167	.753	.307	-.957	.623	-.542	5	.611
Pair 21	PreSEC3 - PostSEC3	-.667	1.211	.494	-1.938	.604	-1.348	5	.235
Pair 22	PreSEC4 - PostSEC4	-1.167	1.329	.543	-2.562	.228	-2.150	5	.084
Pair 23	PreSEC5 - PostSEC5	-.500	.837	.342	-1.378	.378	-1.464	5	.203

The paired samples test table compares the increase or decrease in the scores for different constructs that has occurred after the intervention and the pre-intervention measures. Thus, mean differences across pairs tell us the nature and extent of change; negative values pointing to improvement (post intervention scores are higher) and positive values suggesting decline. Bearing the above analysis in mind, it should come as no surprise that the third and final pair of pre and post intervention self-observations (PreSI3 - PostSI3) reflected the most noteworthy progress in the form of a mean difference of -1.500 which was confirmed by statistical $t = -6.708$ ($t = -6.708$, $p = .001$) to have taken place in the area of relevance to the study. Again, the $p < 0.05$ meaning that there is a statically significant difference and it means that the intervention makes a difference in this particular domain. Some of these include: Pair 16 (PrePAI1 - PostPAI1), mean difference = -0.500, $t = -2.236$, $p = 0.076$) and Pair 22 (PreSEC4 - PostSEC4), mean difference = -1.167, $t = 2.150$, $p = 0.084$) that shows considerable improvement but with a p-value greater than 0. The same is true for emotional regulation in the Pair 10 (PreER1 to PostER1) with the mean difference of 1.000, $t = 1.936$, $p = .111$ indicating that some improvement has occurred in the group, but the results are not statistically significant. In Pair 4 (PreCs1 - PostCs1) and Pair 7 (PreOt1 - PostOt1), the first research questions' changes in mean differences (-0.500 and -.167, respectively) are less influenced by the intervention as measured by a .456 and .822 p-values. Furthermore, some pairs, PreTTR1 - PostTTR1 (mean difference = 0.167, $P = 0.741$) and PreSEC2 - PostSEC2 (mean difference = 0.167, $P = 0.611$), show minimal changes which emphasizes heterogeneity of the intervention methodology on different domains.

At the end, although several constructs, especially peer interaction and independence increased significantly, other changes did not attain statistical significance indicating more hybrid results of the intervention and the need to look further and alter the intervention to achieve optimal results.

Discussion

Since socialization is one of the critical developmental processes in human, it is more significant for children with ID because, they have restricted ability in social

relations, communication, and emotional skills. Art and play are valued by everyone and play has been found useful to support children with ID or ASD cognitively or socially. Such a method can help such children to acquire social/emotional skills that include: compassion, work in groups, and sharing. The social skills of children with ID presented as developmentally delayed because of the inability to participate in normal play and communication play. Play in areas of playgrounds and Virtual environments has to meet these gaps through play activities that employ social interaction and communication. The study therefore calls for the integration of such games in teaching-learning settings as well as in therapeutic interventions since they help inculcate interpersonal relation skills, self-control skills and skills of skills of how to facilitate social interactions. This is the focus of the research; play with directions will increase social processing, peer relationships, and social skills in children with ID. This also assesses the potential and the concern with using physical and computer-based games to this effect. The questions for this research are therefore; how does game affect communication, the interactions and the ability to promote good relation among students. For this reason, the significance of the study is in contributing to the understanding of the context for which play is facilitative for the purposes of increasing its social aspect for children with ID. Its purpose is to assist practitioners, the parents, and the policymakers in improving the organized play opportunities as well as in creating favorable environments that the children with ID might have an opportunity to emulate their social and emotional development. However this study has its own limitations; the sample of the study was a small group and the period of the intervention was short, however these constraints have a low external validity. However, it offers further suggestions concerning the benefits of the organization of play on the enhancement of play skills by children with ID. The study indicates that various averages of social interaction, plus mood and compliance during the play, raised in children after the intervention. Based on this, the researcher concludes that ID children can be helped to develop interactional-communication and physical-small gross motor domain pro-social behaviors more especially if play is well structured physically as well as digitally.

FINDINGS OF STUDY

Demographic Data

1. Age: Respondents ranged from 9 to 15 years, with the majority (33.3%) being 13 years old. Ages 9, 11, 12, and 15 each represented 16.7% of the sample.
2. Gender: 66.7% were female, and 33.3% were male.
3. Grade: 66.7% were in Grade 1, while 33.3% were in Grade 2.

Social Interaction

1. 50% of children initiated conversations (PreSI2).
2. Regular interaction was limited, with only 16.7% reporting consistent engagement.
3. 83.3% initiated interactions, indicating significant improvement.
4. Conversations during gameplay increased to 66.7%.

Communication Skills

1. 50% expressed their thoughts and feelings effectively.
2. Interaction levels were split between initiating conversations and observing.
3. 50% achieved higher competency in expressing thoughts and feelings.
4. Improved clarity and confidence in communication were observed.

Teamwork and Collaboration

1. 50% actively participated in team tasks.
2. Moderate group engagement was noted at 66.7%.
3. Participation in group tasks rose to 66.7%, showing stronger collaboration.
4. Better teamwork and shared responsibilities were observed.

Emotional Regulation

1. 50% demonstrated cooperation in sharing resources.
2. Turn-taking required occasional reminders.
3. Rule compliance improved, with 66.7% showing good understanding.
4. Better cooperation and adherence to rules were noted.

Turn-Taking and Rule Adherence

1. 66.7% experienced moderate peer acceptance.
2. Inclusion levels were somewhat limited.
3. 66.7% formed friendships following gameplay.

4. Improved peer relationships and acceptance were observed.

Peer Acceptance and Inclusion

1. 66.7% played independently but showed moderate confidence.
2. Willingness to take challenges was limited.
3. 100% showed improved confidence, attempting challenges willingly.
4. Children expressed thoughts more clearly and confidently.

Self-Esteem and Confidence

1. 66.7% played independently but showed moderate confidence.
2. Willingness to take challenges was limited.
3. 100% showed improved confidence, attempting challenges willingly.
4. Children expressed thoughts more clearly and confidently.

CONCLUSIONS

The goals of an intervention program for children diagnosed with ID were achieved to a significant extent referring to the positive changes in their social and communication development. Most of the participants demonstrated overall improvement in peer interaction, emotional stability, and engagement in a group setting. This implies that it is possible to promote the crucial activity of social behaviors like use of single lexicon words in initiating conversations ability to maintain eye contact, comprehending signals, turn taking, and regulation of feelings through well-structured and well-targeted approaches. The changes that were noted were not only changes that accessed the children's social capabilities but also changes in confidence and communication that was in them. The results signal more encouraging notes of development although the process was not without inconsistency regarding the progress of the learners. Some kids showed more obvious and fairly distinctive gains than others, proving that without a doubt, kids have different requirements that should be addressed. , the level of severity of ID, the background experience of the children, and the care that they received during the intervention seem to have worked out the outcome.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends that educational institutions should incorporate structured physical and digital games into their curricula to enhance the social interaction, emotional regulation, and peer relationships of children with intellectual disabilities. It is needed to provide professional training for teachers, caregivers, and therapists on implementing structured games effectively. It is suggested to encourage the development and use of adaptive gaming tools that cater to various cognitive and physical needs.

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